

JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH

Department of Pure and Applied Chemistry

Faculty of Physical Sciences

University of Maiduguri

<https://jsrunimaid.com>

Research Article

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10580573>

LEVEL OF SOME HEAVY METALS AND PHYSICOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS IN SOIL SAMPLES FROM SHANI AND KWAYWKUSAR LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREAS, BORNO STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Kwayakusar and Shani local government areas are known for intensive agricultural activities for both commercial and consumption purposes and use tones of agrochemicals for soil amendment to improve harvest. These agrochemicals and other sources introduces heavy metals in the soil, hence, the need to access the level of some heavy metals and physicochemical parameters changes in the soil. Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer was used to determine the concentration of the heavy metals in the soil. Determinations of pH, conductivity, cation exchange capacity (CEC) organic carbon, organic matter, calcium, sodium and potassium were carried out using standard methods. The pH of the soil from the two local government area ranged from 5.74E+00 to 6.54E+00, while electrical conductivity varies from 1.90E+01 to 4.11E+02 μScm^{-1} with the highest concentration being observed in the soil from Gashina agricultural location at Kwayakusar local government area. The levels of cation exchange capacity ranged from 8.09E+00 to 6.92E+01 C.mol/kg with the highest concentration also detected in Gashina agricultural location from Kwayakusar local government area. Organic carbon in the soil samples from the two local governments' agricultural locations ranged from 5.09E-01 to 4.06E+00 %, while organic matter varies from 1.17E+00 to 7.10E+00 %. The maximum percentage of 4.06E+00 % organic carbon was observed in the Gashina agricultural location at Kwayakusar local government area, while the minimum percentage of 5.09E-01 % was observed in the soil from Lukundum agricultural location in Shani local government area. For organic matter, the maximum percentage of 7.00E+00 % was detected in the soil from Gashina agricultural location at Kwayakusar local government area, while the minimum percentage of 1.17E+00 % was observed in the soil from Lukundum agricultural location at Shani local government area. Calcium ranged from 4.60E+00 to 2.10E+01 Mg/Kg; for sodium, it ranged from 5.00E-02 to 3.30E-01 Mg/Kg; while potassium ranged from 1.50E-01 to 2.94 mg/kg. The level of Ca, Na and K in the soil samples from the two Local Government agricultural locations increases with increase in depth. Thus, the concentrations of heavy metals in the soils samples obtained from the present study were higher than the FAO standard.

Keywords: Heavy Metals; Kwayakusar; Shani; Physicochemical; Soil

INTRODUCTION

Soil as a component of terrestrial ecosystems, being essential for the growth of plants is a dynamic system and subject to short term fluctuations, such as variation in moisture status, pH and also undergoing gradual alterations in response to changes in management and environmental factors [1]. The high level of civilization related soil pollution has recently become a major issue and chemical analysis of soil is important for environmental monitoring and legislation [2]. As human activities began to undergo industrialization, the amount of waste thrown into the environment increased tremendously [3]. The combination of population explosion and increasing levels of industrialization and urbanization has led to environmental pollution [4]. Industries have largely been responsible for discharging of effluents containing trace metals such as zinc (Zn), Cadmium (Cd), Mercury (Hg), Lead (Pb) and Chromium (Cr) into our environment [3].

Monitoring the endangerment of soil by heavy metals is of interest due to their influence on ground and surface water [5] and also on flora [6], animals and humans [7]. The overall behavior of heavy metals in soil is said to be governed largely by their sorption and desorption reactions with different soil constituents, especially clay components [8]. The chemical behavior of heavy metals in soils is controlled by a number of processes, including metal cation release from contamination source materials (e.g., fertilizer, sludge, smelter dust, ammunition, slag), cation exchange and specific adsorption onto surfaces of minerals and soil organic matter, and precipitation of secondary minerals [9]. The relative importance of these processes depends on soil composition and pH. In general, cation exchange reactions and complexation to organic matter are most important in acidic soils, while specific adsorption and precipitation become more important at near-neutral to alkaline pH values [10]. [11] studied the trace metal concentrations in some Libyan soils and found that the concentrations of the trace metals in clay surface soil are higher than in sandy soil. The multiple regression analyses performed confirmed the importance of pH as well as other soil properties such as texture, electrical conductivity and organic matter or carbonates on the behaviour of nutrients and heavy metals [12]. Increased anthropogenic inputs of Cu and Zn in soils have caused considerable concern relative to their effect on water contamination [13]. Oxidizing conditions generally increase the retention capacity of metals in soil, while reducing conditions will generally reduce the retention capacity of metals [14]. Soil reduction has been shown to result in the coincident release of metals associated with minerals that are susceptible to reductive dissolution, in particular Mn and Fe oxides [15].

Thus the objective of the study are to determine the concentrations of some heavy metals such as arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), cobalt(Co), copper (Cu), iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), nickel (Ni), lead (Pb) and zinc (Zn),and physicochemical properties such as pH, electrical conductivity (EC) organic carbon percentage, organic matter percentage, cation exchange capacity(CEC), particle size analysis (PSA), and some nutrients which include K^+ , Ca^+ , Na^+ in soil samples of some agricultural location from Kwayakusar and Shani Local Government areas.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sampling Collection Points

The soil samples were collected from different farm lands within the study areas. For Kwayakusar Local Government, the soil samples were collected from Gashina, Wandali and Gusi. For Shani Local Government, the soil samples were collected from Shani and Lakundum. Soil samples were collected at a depth of 0-5cm, 5-10cm and 10-20cm, using spiral auger in a clean polythene bag for

both pre- and post-harvest. All samples were labelled appropriately, stored in cool container and transported to Chemistry Department Laboratory, University of Maiduguri for further analysis. Soil samples from the agricultural locations were collected three times a month for a period of two years.

Samples Preparation

Soil Sample Preparation for Determination of Heavy Metals

The soil samples were oven dried at 105°C for 24 h, followed by grinding and sieving using 0.18 mm sieve. A 0.5 g of dry soil sample was poured into a graduated test tube and mix with 2 mL of aqua regia 1:3 (1 conc. HCl: 3 conc. HNO₃). The mixture was digested on a hot plate at 95°C for 1 h and allowed to cool to room temperature. The sample was then diluted to 10 ml using distilled water and left to settle overnight. The supernatant was filtered prior to analysis using AAS as specified in [16].

Determination of pH and EC in Soil Samples

Ten grams (10g) of soil sample was weighed into a 50ml beaker and 25ml of distilled water was added. The suspension was allowed to stand for one hour with occasional stirring using a glass-rod (stirrer). The pH meter was calibrated using buffer solutions of pH 4 and pH 7.0, before immersed into the supernatant of the suspension. The reading was taken when it was fairly stable without further stirring. The reading was then recorded as “soil pH measured in 1:2.5 soil water ratios”. The electrolytes of the pH meter were rinsed with distilled water and wiped dry with a clean tissue before immersed in distilled water prior to each subsequent measurement. The suspension was then taken in the same manner with the use of an EC meter. The results were recorded in mScm⁻¹.

Determination of Exchangeable Cations (Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Na⁺, and K⁺) in Soil

Ten grams (10g) of air dried soil sample was weighed into a 150ml plastic bottle and 30mls of 1N NH₄OAC (pH 7.0) was added and shake for 2hrs. The extract was filtered into a clean 100ml volumetric flask, 30ml of 1N NH₄OAC was again added to the residue and shake for 30 mins, it was then filtered into the same volumetric flask. Another 30mls of 1N NH₄OAC was added and shaken for 30mins which was filtered into the same volumetric flask. The extract was made up to 100ml with the extracting solution with 1N NH₄OAC [17].

Titrimetric Determination of Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ in Soil

Ten milliliters (10mLs) of the extract above was pipette into a clean 250mL conical flask and 100mls of distilled water was added. 15mL of NH₄ buffer, 10 drops each of KCN, NH₂OH.HCl, K₄Fe (CN)₆ and Tca were also added. Few minutes was allowed for the reaction to take place after which 5 drops of EBT indicator were added and the solution was titrated with 0.01N Na₂ EDTA to a permanent blue colour [17].

Titrimetric Determination of Mg²⁺ in Soil

Ten mills (10mls) of extract was pipette into a clean 250mL conical flask and 100mL of distilled water was added. 10 drops each of KCN, NH₂OH.HCl, K₄Fe (CN)₆ and Tca were also added followed by 10mL of 10% NaOH to raise the pH to 12 or slightly higher. A pinch of murexide indicator was added and the solution was titrated to reddish violet with 0.01N Na₂ EDTA [17].

Calculation

$$\text{Meq Ca}^{2+}/100\text{g soil} = \frac{a \times \text{Tca} \times V_1 \times 100 \times 1000}{W \times V_2 \times \text{eq. wt of Ca}}$$

$$\text{Meq Mg}^{2+}/100\text{g soil} = \frac{a \times T_{\text{mg}} \times V_1 \times 100 \times 1000}{W \times V_2 \times \text{eq. wt of Mg}}$$

Where

a = mLs of 0.01N EDTA was used for titration of sample

T_{ca} = titration factors of EDTA against Ca i.e. $\frac{0.01 \times 40.08}{1000} = 0.0004008$

T_{mg} = titration factors of EDTA against Mg i.e. $\frac{0.01 \times 24.32}{1000} = 0.0002432$

V₁ = total volume of extract

V₂ = mL of aliquot or filtrate

W = weight of sample used

Determination of Sodium and Potassium in Soil

The determination was by flame photometric methods, and the concentration of potassium and sodium (in ppm) of each was directly found from the standard curve. The amount of potassium in the sample (Meq) was calculated using the following formulae [17]. Calculation:

$$\text{Meq K}^+/100\text{g soil} = \frac{\text{ppm from graph} \times \text{d.f} \times 100 \times V}{1000 \times w \times \text{eq. Wt of K}^+}$$

$$\text{Meq Na}^+/100\text{g soil} = \frac{\text{ppm from graph} \times \text{d.f} \times 100 \times V}{1000 \times w \times \text{eq. Wt of Na}^+}$$

Where

w = weight of sample df = dilution factor V = (100) total volume of sample made

Determination of Organic Carbon (Wet Oxidation Method by Walkey Black)

The % O.C was determined by wet oxidation method. 1g of air-dried (passed through 0.5mm sieve) soil sample was weighed into a 250mL conical flask. 10mL of 1N potassium dichromate was added with the help of clean pipette. Using a clean measuring cylinder, 20mL of concentrated sulphuric acid was added. After cooling, 100mL of distilled water was added followed by 10mL of ortho-phosphoric acid (H₃PO₄) and 0.2g of sodium fluoride (NaF). Five (5) drops of diphenylamine indicator was added which turned the colour to deep violet [18].

The excess chromic acid was then titrated with 0.5N ferrous sulphate (1N FeSO₄). The end point was recorded as the colour changed from deep violet to deep green. The same procedure was repeated on the blank (without soil sample). The amount of soil sample was recorded and the strength of the FeSO₄ was titrated and finally the % O.C oxidized by potassium dichromate (K₂Cr₂O₇) was calculated using the formulae below

$$\% \text{ O.C} = \frac{B - T \times F \times 0.39}{W}$$

Where

B = amount of 0.5N FeSO₄ solution required in blank titration

T = amount of 0.5N FeSO₄ solution required in the titration of sample

F = Normality of FeSO₄ and W = weight of soil sample

Statistical Analysis

Data where applicable were analysed using GraphPad Prism. 2016 Model, Version 8.0 for windows (Graphpad Software, 2016). One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test followed by Dunnet’s Multiple Comparison test was used to analyse and compare the results at a 95% confidence level. Results were expressed as mean±standard deviation (SD).

RESULTS

Concentration Levels of Heavy Metals in Soil Samples from Shani and Kwayakusar LGAs

The mean concentrations of heavy metals in soil samples from 0-5, 5-10 and 10-20cm depth in Shani Local Government Area during pre and post-harvest are as presented in Figure 1. The concentrations of Mn ranged between 5.66 and 14.98 mg/kg; 7.57 and 14.54 mg/kg Fe; 0.23 and 1.21 mg/kg Ni; 0.13 and 0.73 mg/kg Co; 0.01 and 0.77 mg/kg Cu; 0.06 and 3.43 mg/kg Zn; 0.13 and 0.77 mg/kg Pb; 0.03 and 0.88 mg/kg Cd and 0.01 and 0.80 mg/kg As. The levels of heavy metals in Shani Local Government agricultural locations are in the following order Mn> Fe > Zn > Ni>Cd> As> Cu >Pb> Co.

The mean concentrations of heavy metals in soil samples from 0-5, 5-10 and 10-20cm depth in Kwayakusar Local Government Area during pre and post-harvest are as presented in Figure 2. The concentrations of Mn ranged between 5.51 and 14.09 mg/kg; 7.23 and 14.50 mg/kg Fe; 0.23 and 1.24 mg/kg Ni; 0.06 and 0.73 mg/kg Co; 0.04 and 1.30 mg/kg Cu; 0.13 and 2.32 mg/kg Zn; 0.19 and 1.64 mg/kg Pb; 0.03 and 1.71 mg/kg Cd and 0.01 and 0.70 mg/kg As. The levels of heavy metals in Kwayakusar Local Government agricultural locations are in the following order Fe >Mn> Zn > Cd>Pb> Cu> Ni > Co > As.

Figure 1: Concentration Levels of Heavy Metals in Soil Samples from Shani LGA

Figure 2: Concentration Levels of Heavy Metals in Soil Samples from Kwayakusar LGA

Physicochemical Parameters for Soil from different Agricultural Locations of Shani Local Government Area during pre-harvest and post-harvest are as presented in Table 1. pH ranged between 5.81E+00 and 6.50E+00; 1.90E+01 and 1.99E+02 μScm^{-1} Conductivity; 5.90E-01 and 1.33E+00 % Organic Carbon; 1.02E+00 and 4.33E+00 % Organic Matter; 1.06E+01 and 2.90E+01 C.mol/Kg CEC; 5.00E+00 and 1.52E+01 mg/kg Ca; 5.00E-02 and 2.40E-01 mg/kg Na and 1.50E-01 and 1.66E+00 mg/kg K.

Physicochemical Parameters for Soil samples from different Agricultural Locations of Kwayakusar Local Government Area during pre-harvest and post-harvest are as presented in Table 2. pH ranged between 5.74E+00 and 6.61E+00; 2.00E+01 and 4.11E+02 (μScm^{-1}) Conductivity; 7.80E-01 and 4.06E+00 %; Organic Carbon; 1.48E+00 and 7.00E+00 % Organic Matter; 7.85E+00 and 6.92E+01 C.mol/Kg CEC; 2.80E+00 and 2.10E+01 mg/kg Ca; 5.00E-02 and 3.30E-01 mg/kg Na and 1.50E-01 and 1.66E+00 mg/kg K.

Table 1: Physicochemical Parameters for Soil from different Agricultural Area of Shani Local Government Area during Pre-Harvest and Post-Harvest

Harvest Periods	Locations	Sample Depth	pH	Conductivity (μScm^{-1})	Organic Carbon (%)	Organic Matter (%)	CEC (C.mol/kg)	Ca (mg/kg)	Na (mg/kg)	K (mg/kg)	
Pre-Harvest Shani	Shani	0-5cm	6.45E+00	5.10E+01	9.80E-01	1.69E+00	2.65E+01	5.40E+00	2.10E-01	2.40E-01	
		5-10cm	6.40E+00	2.40E+01	1.03E+00	1.78E+00	2.83E+01	1.12E+01	2.40E-01	2.20E-01	
		10-20cm	6.27E+00	2.60E+01	7.80E-01	1.34E+00	2.94E+01	1.04E+01	2.30E-01	1.70E-01	
	Lukundum	0-5cm	6.46E+00	2.80E+01	6.80E-01	1.17E+00	1.44E+01	5.80E+00	2.20E-01	3.30E-01	
		5-10cm	6.41E+00	2.30E+01	7.00E-01	1.21E+00	1.10E+01	5.60E+00	2.10E-01	1.90E-01	
		10-20cm	6.50E+00	1.90E+01	5.90E-01	1.02E+00	1.06E+01	5.00E+00	2.00E-01	1.50E-01	
	Total			3.85E+01	1.71E+02	4.76E+00	8.21E+00	1.20E+02	4.34E+01	1.31E+00	1.30E+00
	Post-Harvest	Shani	0-5cm	5.81E+00	1.99E+02	1.33E+00	3.91E+00	2.87E+01	1.28E+01	5.00E-02	1.28E+00
			5-10cm	5.94E+00	1.98E+02	1.17E+00	4.33E+00	2.25E+01	1.52E+01	7.00E-02	9.60E-01
10-20cm			5.89E+00	1.04E+02	1.23E+00	3.97E+00	2.64E+01	1.34E+01	5.00E-02	9.50E-01	
Lukundum		0-5cm	5.95E+00	1.41E+02	6.60E-01	3.67E+00	2.01E+01	1.00E+01	6.00E-02	1.66E+00	
		5-10cm	6.01E+00	9.49E+01	7.60E-01	4.22E+00	1.96E+01	1.20E+01	9.00E-02	1.13E+00	
		10-20cm	6.14E+00	9.33E+01	7.00E-01	4.12E+00	2.90E+01	1.10E+01	1.20E-01	9.20E-01	
Total			3.57E+01	8.30E+02	5.85E+00	2.42E+01	1.46E+02	7.44E+01	4.40E-01	6.90E+00	

Table 2: Physicochemical Parameters for Soil from different Agricultural Area of Kwayakusar Local Government Area during Pre-Harvest and Post-Harvest

Harvest Period	Locations	Sample Depth	pH	Conductivity (μScm^{-1})	Organic Carbon (%)	Organic Matter (%)	CEC (C.mol/kg)	Ca (mg/kg)	Na (mg/kg)	K (mg/kg)
Pre-Harvest	Gashina	0-5cm	5.97E+00	7.07E+01	4.00E+00	6.90E+00	3.31E+01	6.20E+00	2.80E-01	8.20E-01
		5-10cm	6.28E+00	4.11E+02	4.06E+00	7.00E+00	6.92E+01	1.42E+01	3.30E-01	8.20E-01
		10-20cm	6.54E+00	2.38E+02	1.85E+00	3.19E+00	5.80E+01	2.10E+01	2.80E-01	6.70E-01
	Wandali	0-5cm	6.20E+00	3.48E+02	1.95E+00	3.36E+00	7.85E+00	2.80E+00	2.60E-01	5.90E-01
		5-10cm	5.90E+00	3.82E+02	1.99E+00	3.43E+00	1.04E+01	7.80E+00	2.50E-01	7.00E-01
		10-20cm	5.94E+00	3.10E+02	1.77E+00	3.05E+00	8.09E+00	6.20E+00	2.70E-01	4.20E-01
	Gusi	0-5cm	6.52E+00	1.64E+02	1.17E+00	2.02E+00	3.29E+01	6.40E+00	2.50E-01	4.50E-01
		5-10cm	6.48E+00	3.48E+02	9.80E-01	1.69E+00	2.87E+01	5.20E+00	1.80E-01	3.10E-01
		10-20cm	6.29E+00	1.66E+02	8.60E-01	1.48E+00	1.11E+01	4.60E+00	2.50E-01	2.60E-01
			Total	4.98E+01	2.27E+03	1.78E+01	3.06E+01	2.48E+02	6.98E+01	2.10E+00
Post-Harvest	Gashina	0-5cm	6.61E+00	4.60E+01	7.80E-01	4.33E+00	2.79E+01	1.20E+01	1.30E-01	2.92E+00
		5-10cm	6.53E+00	2.50E+01	9.80E-01	4.45E+00	2.24E+01	1.08E+01	8.00E-02	1.28E+00
		10-20cm	6.31E+00	3.30E+01	1.07E+00	3.96E+00	2.47E+01	1.58E+01	1.20E-01	9.50E-01
	Gusi	0-5cm	5.74E+00	1.13E+02	2.20E+00	5.64E+00	3.10E+01	1.48E+01	1.00E-01	2.94E+00
		5-10cm	5.96E+00	5.00E+01	1.27E+00	3.97E+00	1.82E+01	7.60E+00	5.00E-02	1.92E+00
		10-20cm	5.90E+00	4.80E+01	9.80E-01	4.08E+00	2.49E+01	6.20E+00	7.00E-02	1.79E+00
	Wandali	0-5cm	6.31E+00	4.50E+01	1.27E+00	4.10E+00	2.53E+01	1.08E+01	1.10E-01	2.18E+00
		5-10cm	6.05E+00	3.30E+01	1.11E+00	4.11E+00	2.11E+01	7.40E+00	8.00E-02	1.66E+00
		10-20cm	6.14E+00	2.00E+01	1.05E+00	4.20E+00	2.51E+01	7.60E+00	1.00E-01	1.16E+00
		Total	6.18E+01	5.79E+02	1.16E+01	4.03E+01	2.32E+02	9.76E+01	1.09E+00	1.71E+01

DISCUSSION

The pH of the soil from the two local government area ranged from 5.74E+00 to 6.54E+00, while electrical conductivity varies from 1.90E+01 to 4.11E+02 μScm^{-1} with the highest concentration being observed in the soil from Gashina agricultural location at Kwayakusar local government area. The electrical conductivity can be classified as extremely saline; this is in accordance to [20] classification as cited by [21]. [20] classified electrical conductivity as non-saline < 2; moderately saline 2-8; very saline 8-16; extremely saline 16 above. From the result, the pH of the soil was found to be acidic and [22] reported that the mobility and availability of heavy metals is considerably greater in acidic soils than in near neutral or alkaline soils. The levels of Cation exchange capacity ranged from 8.09E+00 to 6.92E+01 C.mol/kg with the highest concentration detected in Gashina agricultural location from Kwayakusar local government area. pH is most influential to govern mobility and availability of metals and it was found that cation exchange capacity of a soil increases with a rise in pH [21]. This is in agreement with the present studies as the cation exchange capacity as well as the pH was observed to decrease with depth, while the heavy metals in the soil was observed to increase with depth in the two local governments agricultural locations. Cation exchange capacity of the soil samples from the two locations was observed to decrease significantly with depth. Organic carbon in the soil samples from the two local governments agricultural locations ranged from 5.09E-01 to 4.06E+00 %, while organic matter varies from 1.17E+00 to 7.10E+00 %. The levels of organic carbon and organic matter decreases significantly with decrease in depth. The maximum percentage of 4.06E+00 % organic carbon was observed in the Gashina agricultural location at Kwayakusar local government area, while the minimum percentage of 5.09E-01 % was observed in the soil from Lukundum agricultural location in Shani local government area. For organic matter, the maximum percentage of 7.00E+00 % was detected in the soil from Gashina agricultural location at Kwayakusar local government area, while the minimum percentage of 1.17E+00 % was observed in the soil from Lukundum agricultural location at Shani local government area. This could be attributed to the decomposition of organic matter due to the agricultural activities. Moreover, the temperature in the study areas must have favoured the activities of microorganism on soil organic matter. Organic carbon and organic matter also influence the solubility and availability of heavy metals in soils [21]. In the present study, it was observed that the organic carbon, organic matter as well as the pH of the soil samples from the two Local Government agricultural locations decreased with depth, while heavy metals was observed to increase with depth. High organic matter content helps in the high retention capacity for many pollutants [22]. Calcium ranged from 4.60E+00 to 2.10E+01 Mg/Kg; for sodium, it ranged from 5.00E-02 to 3.30E-01 Mg/Kg; while potassium ranged from 1.50E-01 to 2.94E+00 Mg/Kg. From the results of the present study it was observed that the level of Ca, Na and K in the soil samples from the two Local Government agricultural locations increases with increase in depth to a level of 20 cm. The calcium content was found to be highest in the soil samples from Gashina agricultural location at Kwayakusar local government area, while the lowest level was detected from the same agricultural location. Na content was found to be highest in the soil samples from Shani agricultural location at Shani local government area and the lowest level was detected at Gashina agricultural location at Kwayakusar local government area. K content was found to be highest in the soil samples from Gashina agricultural location at Kwayakusar local government area and the least level was observed at Lukundum agricultural location from Shani local government area.

The concentrations of heavy metals showed spatial and temporal variations, which may be ascribed to the variation in heavy metal sources and the quantity of heavy metals discharged through

agricultural activities, atmospheric deposition, and vehicular emission. This trend suggests that continuous application of organic and inorganic fertilizer during the pre and post-harvest influenced the soil physicochemical properties. Evidence that heavy metals may move in the soil profile was provided by [23], in their field experiment the researchers used sludge with a high content of heavy metals and found that Zn had moved down to 50 cm, Cd to 17 cm while Ni to 75 cm. [24] measured the metal distribution in the soil profile in a field experiment where sludge had been applied at a rate of 40 t ha⁻¹ and rainfall rate was around 560 mm per annum over a period of 4 years. They found a significant movement of Cd, Ni, Pb and Zn to a depth of 10 cm. Also [25] reported that heavy metals had a uniform distribution in the soil profile to a depth of 1 m, due to their movement. Results such as these tend to have been obtained from the present study, where movement of heavy metals down the soil profile (leaching) to a depth of 20 cm due to application of organic and inorganic fertilizer during pre and post-harvest. The concentrations of heavy metals in the soils samples obtained from the present study were higher than the FAO standard.

CONCLUSION

The result revealed that concentrations of heavy metals showed spatial and temporal variations, which may be ascribed to the variation in heavy metal sources and the quantity of heavy metals discharged through agricultural activities, atmospheric deposition, and vehicular emission. This trend suggests that continuous application of organic and inorganic fertilizer during the pre and post-harvest influenced the soil physicochemical properties.

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